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Executive summary

This document serves as a review and collection of available information about lunar raw water availability, composition, potential contaminations and respective modelling and simulation. Information were gathered from scientific literature, remote sensing data and exchange with international scientists in this area. This information is a prerequisite for the preliminary design of the test setup and also for the development of suitable water and water ice simulants for the validation experiments.

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1 State of water on the Moon

Water present on the lunar surface is currently the focus of the planetary science and space technology communities. Not only can they provide information about the formation of the Solar System, but also do they represent an opportunity to make space travel more inexpensive, opening the way for commercial activities on and around the Moon. Concentration of water in the permanently shaded regions (PSRs) of the South polar region were already hinted at by the Clementine mission in 1996 (Nozette *et al.*, 1996). Subsequently, both the Lunar Crater Observer and Sensing Satellite (LCROSS) Shepherding Spacecraft (Colaprete *et al.*, 2010), as well as Chandrayaan-1 Moon Mineralogy Mapper M(3) (Li *et al.*, 2018) have provided indications of water ice deposits in polar PSRs. Recent developments of lunar water prospecting indicate that its presence might be not limited to PSRs sites and might include both sunlit areas (Honniball *et al.*, 2021) as well as micro cold-traps (Hayne *et al.*, 2020). However, much is still unknown about the exact state of water on the Moon, for example, the exact distribution, form, and concentration of the water inside the lunar regolith is still unknown, as is its origin.

1.1 Permanently shaded regions

In 2009, NASA's LCROSS mission successfully reached its goal of determining the presence of water in the permanently shaded southern polar crater Cabeus. This accomplishment was enabled by collaboration of two spacecraft: a spent Centaur upper stage was purposely directed to impact onto the crater, while the Shepherding Spacecraft carrying a whole array of sensing instruments acquired information on the ejecta plume. The selection of the collision location was guided by multiple factors, concerning both the likelihood of finding water evidence there, as well as its relative position with respect to the Shepherding Satellite and the Sun, enabling illumination of the ejecta at a specific altitude. Previous remote sensing performed by the Lunar Prospector (Feldman *et al.*, 1998) had demonstrated high hydrogen concentration at latitudes over 70° from the equator and Clementine bistatic radar had displayed characteristic icy surfaces reflection features at the South pole. Furthermore, these findings were compliant, due to the small lunar rotation axis inclination with respect to the ecliptic plane, to the location of permanently shadowed regions having temperatures as low as 40 K, then making water ice deposition stable in lunar almost absent atmosphere.

After Centaur struck on the surface, LCROSS spectrometers measured a high temperature (1000 K) ejecta thermal emission, as well as the sunlight scattered by the fragmented particles. Estimates flowing down from these measurements indicate a water ice presence of $5.6 \pm 2.9\%$ by mass (Colaprete *et al.*, 2010). While this finding surely contributes to substantiating the potential of utilization of the lunar water, specifically providing with a figure for the amount that is present, it must be remarked that the sensing only observed a limited area, hence leaving unaddressed the depiction of a wider distribution on the surface. Furthermore, the Shepherding Spacecraft sensing the ejecta from a collision hampered formulating upon the physical state of the surface/subsurface water ice. Combining these limitations of the LCROSS scientific output, it is not possible to distinguish among the numerous existing theories on lunar water origin.

One year prior to the LCROSS discovery, the Chandrayaan-1 lunar probe had also performed analysis on the ejecta from a lunar impactor in a southern polar region, confirming the presence of water Li *et al.* (2018) and Pieters *et al.* (2009) have provided evidence of surface exposed water ice in the PSRs of lunar polar regions, exploiting the M(3) instrument onboard Chandrayaan-1.

Hayne *et al.* (2015) used surface temperature measurements from the Diviner Lunar Radiometer and ultraviolet albedo spectra from the Lyman Alpha Mapping Project (LAMP) Experiment on board LRO to investigate the presence of exposed water ice on the lunar surface. They found for maximum annual surface temperatures above 110 K (H₂O sublimation temperature) no evidence of exposed water ice, but spectral evidences for water ice at some locations with temperatures below 110 K. Their Fig. 4 shows locations of UV albedo spectra suggesting water ice and measured maximum annual surface temperatures by Diviner. The data suggest water ice concentrations of ~0.1-2.0% by mass for ice-regolith mixtures or up to 10% surface area coverage if pure water ice is exposed. The Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter had previously been able to only provide hints of water signatures near the south pole, which could however not be distinguished from OH signatures (Hayne *et al.*, 2015; Lawrence *et al.*, 2011). The near-infrared spectroscopy performed by the M(3)

enabled discriminating between the two molecules by observing the sunlight coming from surrounding topographic features and reflected by the PSRs.

Furthermore, comparison of the spatial distribution of surface exposed water ice to the annual maximum temperatures estimated by the Diviner instrument (Williams *et al.*, 2017), shows high correlation between ice exposures and cold traps, that are locations having temperatures below 110 K during a full lunation.

Figure 1: Green dots represent the pixels yielding ice detection, for both north pole (A) and south pole (B). Courtesy of Li *et al.* (2018).

On one hand this establishes the relevance of low temperatures for enabling water deposition in PSRs, on the other, not all of the cold traps display surface water content. Indeed, only ~3.5% of cold traps exhibit such feature, and according to Li *et al.* (2018) this might be due to a separation in the time scales of water resupply and regolith gardening, the latter occurring with a substantially higher frequency. Li *et al.* (2018) investigated reflectance spectra from the Moon Mineralogy Mapper [M (3)] instrument on board the Chandrayaan-1 spacecraft and studied the detection of near-infrared absorption features that are diagnostic of water ice. Detections were found within 20° latitude of both poles and models of the spectra suggest that these pixels may contain ~30 wt % ice. They mapped the detection results (Figure 1) filtering them according to further criteria, such as maximum annual surface temperature (below 110 K), LOLA albedo measurements and LAMP spectra. Water ice is detected in both the northern and southern polar regions, with a greater number of observations in the south due to the more shaded regions, meaning future missions will likely go to the south pole. Nonetheless, the deposition mechanism as well as the dynamics governing the evolution of cold traps and ice exposures remain unclear. Related to this research is the model created by Reiss *et al.* (2021), where a heat and mass transfer simulations indicate suitable conditions for a water pumping mechanism on the lunar (sub)surface. It shows that water accumulates at around 10 cm depth, and is partially released again during the day. This is consistent with information provided in an overview from (Hurley, 2022), where the depth distribution is investigated. However, an interesting remark was made that the data inferred from the LEND instrument with neutrons suggested that the amount of water at the LCROSS impact site should have been around 0.5%. The depth at which neutron collector could sense is regarded as 1 meter, indicating that the 5% measured from the LCROSS mission originated mostly from a depth below 1 meter.

1.2 Micro cold traps

An investigation conducted by Hayne *et al.* (2020), estimated that the cold traps might cover a larger fraction of the lunar surface than previously expected. Hence, this provides promising insights on the potential for water extraction in future missions. Drawing from the Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter data (Vondrak *et al.*,

2010), the authors developed models to predict lunar shadows and temperatures at small spatial scales, ranging from 1 km down to ≤ 1 cm characteristic lengths. The term "micro cold trap" then represents in the planetary scientists jargon a region of the Moon having a characteristic dimension falling in the aforementioned spectrum, and a temperature permanently below 110 K. These areas are estimated to be representative for $\sim 10 - 20\%$ of overall lunar cold traps.

Using a statistical model of surface topology that is coherent with both temperature and shadows instantaneous distribution, it was possible to extend the theoretical model to simulate the two parameters over the planetary body during a full lunation. Results for the shadows distribution demonstrate a difference in both characteristic lengths and global coverage of PSRs in the two polar regions. While the North pole typically displays 1 km size or smaller crater PSRs, the South hosts larger PSR surface areas that consist of few large size craters. Closely related to this, ice stability is estimated based on the temperatures model. Such correlation, compellingly supported by the experimental evidence of the M(3) instrument, grounds its roots in the steep sublimation increase with temperature. Two different thermal model are proposed for different scales. At small scales, the heat transfer is dominated by lateral thermal conduction, while for larger craters radiation is dominant. In terms of spatial distribution, the results are consistent with the shadows simulation, the South pole having a greater overall cold trap area when compared to the North pole. Furthermore, temperatures tend to exceed 110 K for location at latitudes below 80° N/S, properly establishing it is most likely to find stable water ice in polar regions.

Figure 2: Logarithmic plot of number of PSRs and col traps as provided by the combined shadows/temperature model, against length scale L . Courtesy of Hayne *et al.* (2020).

In conclusion, when looking at the population of lunar PSRs in Figure 2, it is possible to evaluate that the highest number of cold traps are found in the order of centimetres characteristic lengths. Nonetheless, due to their small size, these contribute to only $\sim 2\%$ overall area. Interestingly, the centimetre scale was found to be the lower bound for the existence of cold traps, since below these dimensions lateral conduction becomes substantial, inducing ice instability due to relatively high heat transfer rates.

1.3 Sunlit regions

The Stratospheric Observatory for Infrared Astronomy (SOFIA) mission, operated by NASA and DLR, provided the first proof of water presence in sunlit regions of the southern lunar hemisphere in 2021. The investigation was driven by the multiple observations of absorption features shared by both hydroxyl and water (Clark, 2009). The objective of pointing SOFIA's telescope to the Clavius Crater was to discern between the two substances. Observations were not limited to the southern polar region where water was expected to be found (Li and Milliken, 2017), but also includes an equatorial region where water was not expected as a sanity check of the sensing instrument and of the analysis methodology adopted (Honniball *et al.*, 2022).

The retrieved data show an absorption feature due to the presence of water in sunlit high lunar latitudes (Honniball *et al.*, 2021). The discovery is certainly surprising and it casts the light on how non-shadowed lunar regions with temperatures as high as 120°C can host water molecules. On the other hand, it must be underpinned that the water presence SOFIA has assessed to be present in these regions is estimated to only amount to 100 – 400 μm , which translates to a water content 100 times lower than that of the Sahara Desert (Chou and Hawkes, 2020).

Multiple concurring theories have been developed that would explain the stability of lunar ice at high temperatures and its deposition mechanisms. According to Hibbitts *et al.* (2011), water distribution on the illuminated Moon might be explained by the adsorption of molecular water onto regolith. The thermal stability of water in ultra-high vacuum conditions was experimentally evaluated by dint of temperature-programmed desorption experiments. A competing hypothesis put forward by Daly and Schultz (2018) traces back lunar water ice to materials from asteroids and comets rich in volatiles. The stability of the water in this theory derives from either its confinement in bead-like structures of glasses formed upon impact, or again from chemisorption on the regolith surface. Furthermore, Jones *et al.* (2018) modelled the solar wind induced water cycle on the Moon, using regolith from Apollo samples. It was shown that bombardment of solar emitted protons might set motion to a chain of chemical reactions involving water formation and desorption from metal oxides. In conclusion, while a number of theories might be formulated to support a definitive explanation to the lunar water origin, and specifically to its stability in sunlit regions, no experimental study, model or direct observation has yielded conclusive results yet. Nonetheless, since various researchers reported evidence that chemisorbed water is unlikely to constitute a large part of lunar sunlit water (Hendrix *et al.*, 2019; Poston *et al.*, 2015). Honniball *et al.* (2021) suggest that H₂O molecules must be shielded from the hostile lunar environment by alternative means, such as being trapped in glasses or between regolith grains.

2 Potential contaminants and volatiles

2.1 Soluble Contaminants

Water extracted on the lunar surface may be contaminated with lunar regolith particulates, as reported in the In-Situ Resource Utilization Gap Assessment Report (ISECG, 2021) and the Dust Mitigation Gap Assessment Report (ISECG, 2016). The release of ions from lunar regolith into aqueous solutions is partly experimentally proofed (Eick *et al.*, 1996a; Wallace *et al.*, 2009; Cooper *et al.*, 2011; McKay *et al.*, 2015). The average chemical composition of lunar regolith is 50% SiO₂, 15% Al₂O₃, 10% CaO, 10% MgO, 5% TiO₂, and 5-15% Fe with smaller amounts of Na, K, Cr, and Zr (Loftus *et al.*, 2017). Eick *et al.* (1996a) and Eick *et al.* (1996b) demonstrate an increasing dissolution of the major ions Ca, Mg, Al, Fe, and Si of a lunar basalt simulant and a synthetic lunar glass by decreasing the pH or adding organic acids over 172 and 365 days respectively. The studies by Wallace *et al.* (2009) show the same solubility trends by changing the pH using the lunar dust simulant JSC-1A-vf and additionally increasing the solubility by grinding the simulants (period 72 hours). Experiments with the Apollo 11 soil show a strong ion release of Si, Ca, and Al at a neutral pH and a clumping of the soil particles. The clumped particles cannot be de-agglomerated by sonication or dispersants (Cooper *et al.*, 2011).

The dissolution behaviour and influence of the fully reduced nanophase metallic iron (np-Fe⁰) are not yet entirely studied. np-Fe⁰ within a range of 3 to 33 nm is embedded in the agglutinated glasses and the rims of the regolith grains (Taylor *et al.*, 2005). Studies by Wallace *et al.* (2010) proved a higher chemical reactivity caused by np-Fe⁰ indicated by the production of hydroxyl radical (OH·). They dissolved a nanophase iron simulant in 10 mM terephthalate in phosphate-buffered saline.

2.2 Volatiles

The Lunar Crater Observation and Sensing Satellite (LCROSS) detected volatiles besides the spectral identification of water. NASA's LCROSS mission was launched in 2009 and crashed an upper rocket stage into the crater Cabeus (latitude -84.675°, east longitude 311.281°) while a second spacecraft analysed the generated ejecta plume. Table 2-1 lists the measured compounds by the near-infrared (NIR) and ultraviolet/visible (UV/Vis) spectrometers. The presence of water is scientifically proven, whereas scientists consider the organic compounds of the LCROSS data with caution (Hurley *et al.*, 2016).

Table 2-1: Lunar Volatiles measured by NASA's LCROSS mission (Colaprete *et al.*, 2010).

Compound		Molecules cm ⁻²	Moles per moles water vapor · 100%
Water	H ₂ O	5.1 ± 1.4 E19	100.00
Hydrogen sulphide	H ₂ S	8.5 ± 0.9 E18	16.75
Ammonia	NH ₃	3.1 ± 1.5 E18	6.03
Sulphur dioxide	SO ₂	1.6 ± 0.4 E18	3.19
Ethylene	C ₂ H ₄	1.6 ± 1.7 E18	3.12
Carbon dioxide	CO ₂	1.1 ± 1.0 E18	2.17
Methanol	CH ₃ OH	7.8 ± 4.2 E17	1.55
Methane	CH ₄	3.3 ± 3.0 E17	0.65
Hydroxide	OH	1.7 ± 0.4 E16	0.03

Furthermore, the ultraviolet spectrograph (FUV) part of the Lyman Alpha Mapping Project (LAMP) experiment observed the ejecta plume generated by LCROSS and measured the elements in atomic form (except H₂ and CO). Hurley *et al.* (2012) recalculate the soil mass abundances with the corrected values of Gladstone *et al.* (2010) and a heated average total soil mass of 3150 kg (Colaprete *et al.*, 2010). They define the soil mass abundances be a factor of about 1.7 less than the published values by Gladstone *et al.* (2010). Table 2-2 displays the corrected soil mass abundances of the elements ordered by their condensation behaviour at 10⁻⁴ – 10⁻⁶ atm (Anders, 1977).

Table 2-2: Soil mass abundances of elements detected by LCROSS (Gladstone *et al.*, 2010; Hurley *et al.*, 2012).

Element		Type	Soil mass abundance in %
Boron	B	LTV: low-temperature volatile (<600K)	< 0.02
Carbon	C	LTV	< 0.05
Chlorine	Cl	LTV	< 0.12
Carbon Monoxide	CO	LTV	3.35
Hydrogen	H ₂	LTV	4.48 ^{1*}
Mercury	Hg	LTV	0.71
Nitrogen	N	LTV	< 3.88
Oxygen	O	LTV, SIL: silicate	< 0.01
Manganese	Mn	HTV: High-temperature volatile (600-1300 K)	0.76
Sulphur	S	HTV	< 0.04
Zinc	Zn	HTV	< 1.82
Aluminium	Al	CON: early condensate	< 0.005
Calcium	Ca	CON	0.94
Scandium	Sc	CON	< 0.05
Vanadium	V	CON	< 1.59
Magnesium	Mg	SIL	0.24
Silicon	Si	SIL	< 0.01
Arsenic	As	MET: metal	< 0.01
Gold	Au	MET	< 0.94
Cobalt	Co	MET	< 0.59
Iron	Fe	MET	< 0.29
Phosphorus	P	MET	< 0.02

In addition to Table 2-1 and Table 2-2, Killen *et al.* (2010) reported a sodium (Na) release by the LCROSS impact of 1.5 ± 1 kg or a soil mass abundance of 0.05 wt% of Na with a total ejected mass of 3150 kg. Due to the chemical composition of lunar regolith (0.4 wt% Na), the released Na should be magnitudes higher. Killen *et al.* (2010) suppose an incomplete degassing of Na from the regolith or a degassing from a Na/ice mixture.

¹ presents the value from Gladstone *et al.* (2010) times 3.2 due to no correction in Gladstone (2011) but a corrected total soil mass.

3 Modelling of (icy) regolith and extraction processes

3.1 Lunar regolith thermal models

Lunar regolith thermal models solve the heat transfer equation and take as input the physical and thermo-physical properties of the regolith. In most models, the problem is described as one-dimensional and the temperature is determined as a function of depth. Existing thermal models for the lunar regolith differ in the models used to describe the regolith properties, and the models have a critical influence on the modelled temperatures. The thermal models presented below describe the dry regolith without the presence of ice.

The current thermal model for the lunar regolith was developed by Hayne *et al.* (2017) and uses an empirical description with the H -parameter for the variation of bulk density ρ and thermal conductivity k with depth z .

$$\rho(z) = \rho_d - (\rho_d - \rho_s)e^{-\frac{z}{H}}$$

$$k(z, T) = k_d - (k_d - k_s)e^{-\frac{z}{H}} (1 + BT^3)$$

Small H values lead to higher bulk densities and thermal conductivity values in the near-surface layers. The description is based on the work of Vasavada *et al.* (2012), who fitted a simpler thermal model to measured lunar equatorial brightness temperatures. The bulk density values at the surface ρ_s and at large depths ρ_d ($z \gg H$) are fixed values and the H -parameter determines the increase of bulk density with depth. Similarly, in the thermal conductivity model, the contact thermal conductivity of the surface layer k_s and in deep layers k_d is fixed and the thermal conductivity is described as a function of depth z and temperature T , where the H -parameter is the only free parameter. The heat capacity is temperature dependent and modelled by a polynomial fit to measurements on lunar regolith samples.

$$c(T) = c_0 + c_1T + c_2T^2 + c_3T^3 + c_4T^4$$

Other required input values describing the lunar regolith are the albedo and the infrared emissivity. In the model, the first meter of the lunar subsurface is divided into several layers, the one-dimensional heat transfer equation is solved and the regolith temperature is determined as a function of depth. The only free parameter is the H -parameter and Hayne *et al.* (2017) created global maps of this parameter by comparing their model with brightness temperature measurements from the Diviner Lunar Radiometer Experiment (Paige *et al.*, 2010).

One of the uncertainties of thermal models simulating regolith in general stems from the fact that the thermophysical properties of the lunar regolith, namely the heat capacity and the thermal conductivity, have not been measured for temperatures below 100 K. Current models extrapolate the higher temperature data to lower temperatures. Woods-Robinson *et al.* (2019) derived parametrisations of low-temperature lunar regolith properties, based on solid-state physics and measurements of lunar simulant materials. They showed that, for temperatures below 150 K, the thermal conductivity values are nearly an order of magnitude lower than for high temperatures, which results in a lower heat loss rate during night. The thermophysical properties of the material at low temperatures are especially important for modelling the permanently shadowed regions at the lunar poles, where temperatures of ~ 20 K can be approached (see, e.g., Aye *et al.* (2013)).

Martinez and Siegler (2021) built upon the work of Woods-Robinson *et al.* (2019) and updated the thermal conductivity model in order to include both the observed surface temperature trends in warmer equatorial and in cooler polar regions. Incorporated in the model from Hayne *et al.* (2017), they find cooler night time surface temperatures and steeper temperature gradients with depth.

Recently, 3D thermal models were developed combining the 1D H -parameter description and 3D shadowing effects and scattering of radiation. Wilcoski *et al.* (2022) investigate the thermal environment of lunar pits and caves at high latitudes, and King *et al.* (2020) model regolith temperatures at possible landing sites near the lunar south pole to study ice stability.

A microphysical thermal model that more directly simulates regolith properties, such as grain size or bulk density, is currently being developed at the TU Braunschweig (Bürger *et al.*, 2022). In the one-dimensional

thermal model, the regolith bulk density profile is described by the stratification model of Schrapler *et al.* (2015). The steepness of the transition from the surface layer density to the deep layer density is described by the parameter Δ . Small Δ -values indicate a steep transition and with increasing Δ -values the transition becomes smoother. In addition, the stratification model is a function of grain radius. The thermal conductivity is modelled as a function of temperature, grain radius and volume filling factor according to Gundlach and Blum (2012), who developed a thermal conductivity model for a granular packing of equally sized spheres in vacuum.

$$\lambda = \lambda_{\text{net}} + \lambda_{\text{rad}} = \lambda_{\text{solid}}(T) H(T, r, \phi) + B(r, \phi)T^3$$

The heat is transported through the network of solid grains and by radiation in the void spaces of the packing. The conductivity of the solid material $\lambda_{\text{solid}}(T)$ gets reduced by the Hertz-factor $H(T, r, \phi)$ considering the reduced heat flux through the contacts between the particles. The radiative contribution depends on the mean free path of the photons and is therefore also a function of grain radius and volume filling factor. Radiation increases with large grain sizes and small volume filling factors. The fit of this model to in-situ experiments and laboratory measurements on returned lunar samples has not yet been completed. The heat capacity is modelled as a function of temperature following Hayne *et al.* (2017). By considering their difference in albedo (Feng *et al.*, 2020) and grain density (Kiefer *et al.*, 2012), the lunar highlands and maria are modelled separately. The current free parameters in the thermophysical model are the grain radius, the transition width Δ and the deep layer density.

Similar and further descriptions of the thermal conductivity of a packing of equally sized spheres as a function of temperature, grain size and volume filling factor have also been developed by e.g., Sakatani *et al.* (2017), Arakawa *et al.* (2019) and Ryan *et al.* (2022). Another thermal conductivity model considering the composition, particle size, particle shape, volume filling factor, temperature and lithostatic pressure is presented in Wood (2020). A recent study by Persson and Biele (2022) investigates the heat transfer between rough particles and suggest that the models described above are unrealistic for rough particles such as regolith.

3.2 Icy-regolith mixtures models

Thermal models describing the dry lunar regolith can help predict areas where water ice remains stable. However, to study, for example, the thermal extraction of water, the ice must be explicitly included in the models. In the following, an overview of existing approaches will be given.

Siegler *et al.* (2012) conducted thermal conductivity and heat capacity measurements on an icy regolith simulant in the laboratory. Their thermal conductivity measurements are best fit by a linear volume mixing model between ice and dry regolith

$$\lambda = \lambda_{\text{dry}} + \varepsilon_0 \lambda_{\text{ice}} F$$

with the thermal conductivity of the dry regolith λ_{dry} , the thermal conductivity of the bulk ice λ_{ice} , the pore volumetric filling fraction F of the ice and the porosity ε_0 . Another model for the thermal conductivity of icy regolith was proposed by Mellon *et al.* (2004), who assume that ice initially forms at the grain contacts, resulting in necks that increase the conduction through the bulk solid. The thermal conductivity is then a function of the square-root of the volumetric filling factor.

$$\lambda = (1 - \sqrt{F})\lambda_{\text{dry}} + \sqrt{F}\lambda_{\text{ice}}$$

According to Hobbs (2010), the thermal conductivity of ice as a function of temperature can be described as

$$\lambda_{\text{ice}}(T) = \left(\frac{488.19}{T} + 0.4685 \right) \text{Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1} .$$

The volumetric mixing model can also be applied for the heat capacity of icy regolith (e.g., (Siegler *et al.*, 2012; Wasilewski, 2021).

$$c = \frac{F \varepsilon_0 c_{\text{ice}}(T) \rho_{\text{ice}} + c_{\text{dry}}(T) \rho_{\text{bulk}}}{\rho}$$

Parametrizations for the heat capacity of ice can be found in, e.g., Klinger (1981), Fukusako (1990) and Shulman (2004). The approximation by Klinger (1981) reads

$$c_{ice}(T) = (7.49 T + 90) \text{ J kg}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1},$$

but is only valid for temperatures > 100 K. Shulman (2004) presents an approximation that also applies to very low temperatures.

$$c_{ice}(T) = 7.73 \cdot 10^{-3} T (1 - e^{-1.263 \cdot 10^{-3} T^2}) \cdot (1 + e^{-3\sqrt{T}} \cdot 8.47 \cdot 10^{-3} T^6 + 2.0825 \cdot 10^{-7} T^4 e^{-4.97 \cdot 10^{-2} T})$$

Under the assumption that the ice accumulates uniformly in the pores, the bulk density of the icy regolith is the sum of the ice bulk density $\rho_{b,ice}$ and the regolith bulk density $\rho_{b,dry}$.

$$\rho_{bulk} = \rho_{b,dry} + \rho_{b,ice}$$

Finally, in order to describe the heat transfer in icy regolith mixtures, an additional term Q must be included in the heat transfer equation, which takes heat sources and sinks into account.

$$\rho c \frac{dT}{dt} - \frac{d}{dx} \left[\lambda \frac{dT}{dx} \right] = Q$$

If the icy regolith undergoes heating, the water ice sublimates and therefore the effective material properties described above will change. This phase change is included in some thermal models describing the thermal extraction of lunar volatiles, e.g., in Wasilewski (2021), Schieber *et al.* (2022) or Metzger *et al.* (2020).

3.3 Models of water vapour transfer through porous regolith

This section summarizes the transport mechanisms of gas (e.g., water vapour) through the regolith.

In general, there are advective and diffusive transport processes, the former are driven by a pressure gradient and therefore dominating at high pressures and the latter are driven by a thermal gradient. The different transport processes are summarized in Schweighart *et al.* (2021) and presented in the following.

The different flow regimes are characterized by the Knudsen number

$$Kn = \frac{\lambda}{d_p}$$

with the particles' mean free path λ and the pore diameter d_p . The dimensionless number determines whether molecular-molecular collisions ($Kn \ll 0.01$) or molecule-wall collisions ($Kn \gg 1$) dominate. In the transition region there is a combination of both.

The viscous (Darcy) flow describes the gas transport driven by a pressure gradient. The gas behaves like a viscous fluid if molecule-molecule collisions dominate over molecule-wall collisions and the diffusion of different species with regard to each other can be neglected. The viscous particle flux

$$J^v = -\frac{n B}{\mu} \nabla p$$

is a function of the gas permeability B , the dynamic viscosity μ , the total gas pressure p and the molecular number density n .

Inter-species molecular diffusion of atoms or molecules occurs due to different flow velocities of each species and depends on the concentration gradients and the interaction with the other species. The molar flux of species 1 in a binary system is given by

$$J_1^D = -D_{12}^D \nabla n_1 + \frac{n_1}{n} (J_1^D + J_2^D)$$

with the molar number density n , the molecular diffusion coefficients of species 1 moving through species 2 D_{12}^D and the molecular flux of species i J_i^D .

The Knudsen flow occurs at low gas densities and/or small pore sizes where molecule-wall collisions dominate over molecule-molecule collisions. This is the case for a Knudsen number $Kn \gg 1$.

The molar flux of species i is given by

$$J_i^K = -D_i^K \nabla n_i$$

with D_i^K being the Knudsen diffusion coefficient.

In the case of the lunar regolith (small voids) and the very low pressures on the lunar surface, Knudsen diffusion dominates. However, external heating and the increase of the gas pressure due to outgassing of volatile components can cause the transition region or even the viscous flow regime to dominate (Reiss, 2018; Schieber *et al.*, 2020). The total gas flux can be determined as the sum of the viscous and Knudsen flow.

$$J = J^v + J^K$$

Schieber *et al.* (2020) investigated the flow of noncondensing gases and present an advection diffusion model for gas transport in a regolith simulant. They state that the flow of water vapour is more complex, as phase changes and adsorption/desorption are involved.

3.4 Water extraction modelling and simulation

Water extraction simulations combine knowledge from the lunar regolith thermal models together with specific designs for water extraction, and provide a measure of their effectiveness or give insight into potential issues. Reiss (2018) and Biswas *et al.* (2020) both developed a model to predict volatile evolution in the context of sampling lunar rovers. Especially Reiss (2018) provided a sophisticated thermal conductivity model, including interdependencies of gas and solid conductivity, and displayed a comprehensive mass transfer model including sorption processes. Closely related to this model is also the work of Smolka *et al.* (2021).

Based on that, some scholars have started working on different modelling approaches for the thermal extraction of water ice. Early simulation studies covering mainly the heat transfer process in icy deposits are presented by e.g. Fanale *et al.* (1990). More recent studies are e.g. from Metzger *et al.* (2020), who examined the evolution of water ice in the context of sampling lunar rovers applying an extraction concept similar to the “corer”, which is a double-walled heated auger first presented by Zacny *et al.* (2016). The heat transfer model presented by the authors follows a novel approach and is based on the Crank-Nicholson algorithm. Brisset *et al.* (2020) investigated an in-situ extraction method supplemented by heated rods to facilitate the conduction with a coupled heat and mass transfer and simplified water vapor model. Yet, the authors made some course approximations for some major thermophysical properties of the lunar regolith. For the corresponding literature, especially the applied value for the thermal conductivity of lunar soil is rather high, which is expected to fundamentally alter the compiled results of the study. The same extraction method was modelled by Song *et al.* (2021), who also included the collection of water vapor after the withdrawal. Still, the combined heat and mass transfer model is greatly simplified. Another concept for in-situ thermal extraction was examined by Schieber *et al.* (2022), which differs from previous works as the secondary optics were eliminated and replaced with a highly absorptive ceramic that transfers heat to the icy regolith. Concerning the mathematical approach in calculating the coupled heat and mass transfer mechanisms, this model is comparable to Reiss (2018) and extended for icy regolith.

However, none of the described models cover the migration of the phase change interface, or sublimation front, sufficiently, resulting in a significant knowledge gap. This problem is first tackled by Wasilewski (2021), who focused on the behaviour of said interface, namely its location, velocity, and acceleration in various scenarios, in a PSR environment during surface thermal mining. Table 3-1 provides an overview of the existing simulation approaches to the goals of this work.

Table 3-1: Overview of existing simulation approaches concerning the goals of this work.

	Wasilewski (2021)	Reiss (2018)	Smolka et al. (2021)	Schieber et al. (2022)	Brisset et al. (2020)	Song et al. (2021)	Metzger (2018)	Metzger et al. (2020)
Accuracy of thermophysical soil properties								
Inclusion icy regolith	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Heat transfer modeling	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Mass transfer modeling	Partly	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partly	No	Yes
Phase change modeling	Yes	No	Partly	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
Sublimation front display	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
Applicability to LUWEX								
not met hardly met partly met largely met fully met								

4 References

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